

MaskingOPS: A Tutorial for Navigating Video De-identification and Analytic Utility Workflows in Behavioral Research

Journal:	<i>Behavior Research Methods</i>
Manuscript ID	BR-TSC-26-051
Manuscript Type:	Tutorial Special Collection
Date Submitted by the Author:	31-Mar-2026
Complete List of Authors:	Owoyele, Babajide; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems; Radboud Universiteit, Center for Language Studies Schilling, Martin; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems Riedel, Tim; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems Shaikh, Sharjeel; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems Zafari, Zainab; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems Pouw, Wim; Tilburg University, Department of Cognitive Science and Artificial Intelligence de Melo, Gerard; Hasso-Plattner-Institut fur Digital Engineering gGmbH, Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems

1
2
3 **MaskingOPS: A Tutorial for Navigating Video**
4 **De-identification and Analytic Utility Workflows**
5 **in Behavioral Research**
6
7
8
9

10 Babajide Alamu Owoyele^{1,2,*} Martin Schilling² Tim Riedel² Sharjeel Shaik^{2,3}
11 Zainab Zafari^{2,3} Wim Pouw⁴ Gerard de Melo^{2,3}
12

13
14 ¹Centre for Language Studies, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

15 ²Hasso Plattner Institute, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

16 ³University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

17 ⁴Department of Cognitive Science and Artificial Intelligence, Tilburg University, Tilburg, The Netherlands
18

19 *Corresponding author: Babajide Alamu Owoyele

20 Email: babajide.owoyele@hpi.de
21
22

23 **Running Head:** MaskingOPS: Video De-identification and Analytic Utility
24

25 **Word Count:** ~12,000 (including references and appendices)
26
27

28 **Article Type:** Tutorial Paper
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

MaskingOPS: A Tutorial for Navigating Video De-identification and Analytic Utility Workflows in Behavioral Research

Babajide Alamu Owoyele^{1,2*}, Martin Schilling², Tim Riedel²,
Sharjeel Shaik^{2,3}, Zainab Zafari^{2,3}, Wim Pouw⁴, Gerard de Melo^{2,3}

^{1*}Centre for Language Studies, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The
Netherlands.

²Hasso Plattner Institute, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany.

³University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany.

⁴Tilburg University, Tilburg, The Netherlands.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): babajide.owoyele@hpi.de;

Contributing authors: martin.schilling@student.hpi.de;

tim.riedel@hpi.de; sharjeel.shaik@uni-potsdam.de; zainab.zafari@hpi.de;

w.pouw@tilburguniversity.edu; gerard.demelo@hpi.de;

Abstract

Video data is central to behavioral research across psychology, communication science, and human-computer interaction, yet its use raises significant privacy concerns that limit data sharing and reproducibility. Researchers face two interconnected operational challenges: (1) how to de-identify video recordings while preserving behaviorally relevant information, and (2) how to verify that de-identification has not compromised downstream analyses such as pose estimation. This tutorial introduces MaskingOPS, an integrated workflow combining MaskAnyone—a flexible video de-identification framework combining YOLO, SAM2, and pose estimators (MediaPipe, OpenPose)—with MaskBench, an open-source benchmarking framework for evaluating pose estimation quality on both raw and masked videos. We provide step-by-step guidance for the complete pipeline: from video upload and masking strategy selection, through de-identification processing, to systematic assessment of analytic utility using standardized accuracy and kinematic metrics. Through worked examples on naturalistic video data, we demonstrate that Gaussian blurring preserves 88–95% of pose estimation quality (PCK) across estimators, while pixelation and solid fills

show estimator-dependent degradation. We conclude with practical recommendations for selecting masking strategies, choosing pose estimators, and integrating privacy-preserving workflows into FAIR data management practices. All code, configurations, and sample data are freely available at <https://github.com/MaskAnyone/MaskAnyone> (MaskAnyone) and <https://github.com/maskbench/maskbench> (MaskBench).

Keywords: privacy, video analytics, behavioral science, de-identification, pose estimation, benchmarking, GDPR compliance, FAIR data, open science

1 Introduction

1.1 Video as Data in Behavioral Research

Video data has become central to behavioral research across psychology, communication science, and human-computer interaction, offering rich insights into human interactions and behaviors [1]. Researchers in cognitive psychology, developmental psychology, clinical psychology, and related fields increasingly rely on video recordings to study naturalistic behaviors that cannot be captured through self-reports or controlled settings alone. For example, pose estimation from 2D videos can reveal movement synchronization under conditions that may not be observable in laboratory environments [2]. The integration of machine learning and computer vision further enhances video analysis, enabling automated pattern recognition and bridging data-driven and theory-driven research [3].

Beyond methodological advances, video data promotes transparency and reproducibility in research. Sharing videos of research procedures provides a gold standard for documentation, addressing longstanding concerns about replicability [4]. Platforms like Databrary facilitate video data sharing, fostering collaboration and maximizing research impact [5].

However, video data contains inherently identifiable information about participants, making it difficult to share datasets across institutions or make them publicly available for replication studies. Privacy concerns severely limit data sharing and collaborative research efforts. It has been argued that too much video data is currently deleted—which can be considered unethical, as resources are wasted, the potential of data reusability is negated, and reproducibility of research findings is made impossible [6, 7]. Video masking methods can support responsible data sharing, collaboration, and research progress, but researchers need principled ways to evaluate how different privacy-preserving techniques affect the accuracy and reliability of downstream analyses.

1.2 Two Operational Challenges

Researchers working with video data face two interconnected operational challenges that this tutorial addresses.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
Challenge 1: De-identifying video data effectively. The core challenge of video de-identification is the inherent privacy-utility trade-off [8, 9]. Techniques like blurring or pixelation may remove essential contextual information necessary for behavioral analysis [10], while more aggressive obfuscation renders the video unusable from a research standpoint. Further compounding this challenge is the sheer volume of data involved: manual de-identification is impractical for video, and automated approaches must contend with occlusions, fast movements, frame transitions, and temporal continuity [11]. A single insufficiently masked frame can compromise privacy, rendering the entire effort ineffective.

13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
Challenge 2: Verifying that masking preserves analytical quality. Even when de-identification succeeds, masking changes the pixel data that downstream analysis tools rely on. Pose estimation algorithms may behave differently on blurred, pixelated, or solid-fill masked videos compared to raw recordings. Researchers need standardized methods to quantify how much accuracy is lost and whether the remaining signal is sufficient for their analyses. Without reliable evaluation metrics, it is difficult to quantify the balance between privacy and utility, making it harder to develop and justify effective solutions [12].

21
22
23
24
25
These two challenges are rarely addressed together. Masking tools typically operate without built-in utility assessment, while benchmarking frameworks focus on pose estimation accuracy under ideal conditions without considering privacy constraints. This gap leaves researchers without a principled way to make informed decisions about their privacy-preserving workflows.

26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
A recent example illustrates what is at stake. The 2026 Video-based Seizure Detection Challenge [13] asks participants to detect infantile epileptic spasms from smartphone recordings of infants. To protect privacy, the organisers extracted MediaPipe pose landmarks and shared only the resulting coordinate arrays (.npy files)—participants never see the original video. This approach protects identity but discards the rich visual context that could inform model development: researchers cannot inspect how a child moves, verify that a landmark was tracked correctly, or detect artefacts caused by blankets or camera motion. Had the organisers instead applied video masking (e.g., blurring faces while preserving body movement), they could have shared *viewable* masked clips alongside the pose data, giving participants richer input without exposing identity. A benchmarking step would then confirm that the chosen masking strategy does not degrade the very pose signals the challenge relies on. This pattern—*mask the video, verify the signal, share both*—is precisely the workflow that MaskingOPS provides.

40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 **1.3 Introducing MaskingOPS**

This tutorial introduces MaskingOPS, an integrated workflow that addresses both challenges within a single end-to-end pipeline. MaskingOPS combines two open-source tools:

- **MaskAnyone** — an open-source video de-identification platform [14] combining YOLO for detection, SAM2 [15] for segmentation and tracking, and MediaPipe or

OpenPose for pose estimation. It handles masking of both persons and objects in video recordings, with support for human-in-the-loop refinement.

- **MaskBench** — a modular benchmarking framework for evaluating pose estimation quality on both raw and masked videos, supporting seven pose estimators and comprehensive accuracy and kinematic metrics.

Together, these tools form an operational pipeline: *mask it*, then *verify it*, then *share it*. Researchers de-identify their videos with MaskAnyone, assess the impact on downstream analysis with MaskBench, and iterate on their masking strategy until both privacy protection and analytical quality meet their requirements. The resulting masked data, along with extracted pose information and quality reports, can then be archived in compliance with FAIR data principles.

Crucially, each tool is useful on its own: MaskAnyone can be used independently for video de-identification, and MaskBench can be used independently for benchmarking pose estimators on any dataset. Used together, they enable a workflow in which masked *video*—not just extracted features—can be shared with the research community, preserving the rich visual context that raw coordinate arrays alone cannot convey, while providing empirical evidence that the masking has not compromised the signals of interest. Figure 1 illustrates this end-to-end workflow.

Fig. 1: Overview of the MaskingOPS workflow. Researchers de-identify video with MaskAnyone (*mask it*), verify quality with MaskBench (*verify it*), and archive FAIR-compliant data (*share it*). A feedback loop allows iterating on the masking strategy until both privacy and quality requirements are met.

1.4 Tutorial Overview and Audience

This tutorial is designed for behavioral researchers, data stewards, and research support staff who work with video data but do not necessarily have expertise in computer vision or machine learning. By the end of this tutorial, readers will be able to:

- De-identify video recordings using MaskAnyone, selecting appropriate masking strategies for their research context
- Evaluate and compare pose estimation quality across raw and masked videos using MaskBench
- Interpret accuracy and kinematic metrics to make informed decisions about privacy-utility trade-offs

- Integrate privacy-preserving workflows into FAIR-compliant data management practices

The tutorial assumes basic familiarity with running software on a computer but does not require programming expertise. Both tools are deployed via Docker containers, ensuring reproducibility across different computing environments.

To illustrate the breadth of scenarios where MaskingOPS applies, we present three vignettes drawn from active research contexts. These are revisited in Section 5 when we discuss recommended configurations.

Table 1: Illustrative research vignettes for the MaskingOPS workflow.

Scenario	Challenge	MaskingOPS Approach
Clinical: Infant seizure detection	Smartphone videos of infants with epileptic spasms must be shared for AI model development. Current practice: share only extracted pose landmarks (.npy), discarding visual context [13].	Blur infant faces while preserving body movement; verify with MaskBench that pose signals survive masking; share masked video clips alongside pose data so researchers can inspect movements visually.
Educational: Classroom observation	Teacher training videos must anonymise pupils while keeping the teacher identifiable (with consent). Different masking levels needed for different individuals in the same scene.	Use MaskAnyone’s per-person masking with human-in-the-loop refinement to selectively mask pupils; apply solid fill for stronger anonymisation; verify with MaskBench that pupil body language (e.g., engagement posture) remains analysable in the masked output.
Multi-site: Gesture research	A gesture and interaction study runs across three universities with different cameras and lighting. Labs need to share video data through a common repository while ensuring comparable masking quality.	Each lab masks locally with MaskAnyone using a shared blur preset; runs MaskBench to confirm comparable pose estimation quality across sites; archives masked videos with quality reports and provenance metadata to an institutional or domain repository (e.g., DANS).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background on the privacy-utility trade-off, video de-identification techniques, pose estimation, and quality metrics. Section 3 presents Part I of the tutorial: de-identifying video with MaskAnyone. Section 4 covers Part II: assessing analytic utility with MaskBench. Section 5 introduces the integrated MaskingOPS workflow and its connection to research data management. Section 6 discusses advanced topics including batch processing and extensibility. Section 7 addresses limitations and ethical considerations, and Section 8 concludes with practical recommendations.

2 Background

2.1 The Privacy-Utility Trade-Off in Video Data

In an ideal scenario, all personal information would be removed during de-identification while the data remains valuable for its intended use—a masked video that cannot be linked to any individual but still supports behavioral analysis [4]. In practice, however, behavior and identity are deeply intertwined: body shape, gesturing style, and movement patterns can all serve as identifying features. As such, the correct term for masking technology is *pseudo-de-identification*, acknowledging the theoretical possibility of identification through behavioral recognition.

The privacy-utility trade-off manifests differently depending on the masking technique employed. Blurring and pixelation still reveal features like skin tone, posture, and clothing. Solid-fill approaches offer stronger privacy but retain clues from body shape and movement. More aggressive obfuscation renders the video unusable for research purposes [16, 17]. Meanwhile, the use of video in behavioral research raises ethical concerns around privacy, informed consent, and data security [18, 19]. Video recordings often capture not only participants but also bystanders, clinicians, and researchers who may not have consented to be recorded. Data security is critical, as breaches can lead to significant privacy violations [20].

Figure 2 summarises the meta-requirements that any video de-identification solution must balance: privacy protection, analytical utility, and technical robustness.

Fig. 2: Meta-requirements for video de-identification, organised into three pillars. Any masking solution must balance privacy protection, analytical utility, and technical robustness. The relative weighting depends on the research context and data-sharing scenario.

These considerations have led to growing calls in the research community for better data management practices. A recent policy analysis argues that audio and video

recordings should not be destroyed by default but rather managed responsibly through de-identification [6]. Furthermore, in areas like clinical behavioral assessment, masking could enable crowd-sourced annotations while protecting participant privacy, benefiting machine learning model training [21]. Video masking can also reduce the risk of personal information leaks during data breaches in institutional repositories.

2.2 Video De-identification Techniques

De-identifying video data requires both detecting identity-revealing features and applying methods to obscure them. Detection approaches range from object detection with YOLO [22, 23] to person segmentation with models like BlazePose [24] and the Segment Anything Model [25]. Once subjects are identified, several obfuscation methods can be applied, each with distinct trade-offs:

Table 2: Comparison of video de-identification techniques.

Technique	Advantages	Limitations
Blurring	Fast; preserves shape and context	Reveals skin tone, clothing; low intensity may be insufficient
Pixelation	Simple; adjustable intensity	Similar to blurring; identity clues remain at low intensities
Solid fill	Strong privacy; clean visual result	Removes texture and contextual detail
Contour / silhouette	Preserves shape; removes texture	Gait and body shape may still be identifying
Skeleton overlay	Retains full pose information	Background context lost; movement style can be identifying
Face swapping	Preserves expressions; natural appearance	Ethical concerns; computational cost; may fail in complex scenes

Direct methods like blurring and pixelation are fast but often leave identifying clues visible regardless of intensity [26, 27]. Face-swapping techniques (e.g., based on GANs [28]) maintain facial expressions while hiding identity, and full-body methods like DeepPrivacy 2 [29] can replace both face and body using generative models. FAKER [30] takes a complementary approach: extracting human keypoints to drive full-body anonymization in real time, removing skin colour, clothing, and body shape while preserving pose information. Tools like the Red Hen Anonymizer [31] integrate multiple techniques including audio anonymization. Recent studies have begun to quantify how anonymisation affects downstream tasks. Abdulaziz and Bondarev [32] evaluated blurring, masking, encryption, and avatar replacement on video anomaly detection, finding that some detection models unexpectedly performed *better* on anonymised data. Triess et al. [33] applied DeepPrivacy2-based anonymisation to industrial footage and assessed its impact on pose estimation and action recognition, demonstrating that synthetic identity replacement can preserve analytical utility while providing

strong privacy. These findings underscore that the impact of de-identification on downstream analysis depends on the specific algorithm, obfuscation method, and task—reinforcing the need for systematic benchmarking of masking strategies, which is a core contribution of MaskingOPS.

The most promising approaches for behavioral research combine segmentation-based masking with separate pose estimation, allowing researchers to choose the privacy-utility balance appropriate for their specific context [14].

Table 3 compares existing video de-identification tools relevant to behavioral research. To our knowledge, MaskAnyone is the first open-source framework to combine full-body segmentation-based masking, integrated pose estimation, and a modular benchmarking component.

Table 3: Comparison of video de-identification tools for behavioral research.

Tool	Body	Face	Pose	Audio	QA
DeepPrivacy 2	✓	✓	—	—	—
FAKER	✓	✓	—	—	—
Red Hen Anon.	—	✓	—	✓	—
roop	—	✓	—	—	—
OpenPose + blur	—	—	✓	—	—
MaskAnyone	✓	✓	✓	—	✓*

Body = full-body masking; Pose = integrated pose estimation; QA = benchmarking.

*Via MaskBench integration.

2.3 Pose Estimation for Non-Specialists

Human pose estimation involves detecting and tracking the spatial locations of key body joints (keypoints) in images or video sequences [34]. A typical pose model outputs a set of 2D coordinates for joints such as shoulders, elbows, wrists, hips, knees, and ankles, often following the COCO format [35] (17 keypoints) or extended variants with additional joints. Each detected keypoint is typically accompanied by a confidence score indicating the model’s certainty.

Modern approaches fall into two categories. *Top-down* methods first detect individual persons in the image (e.g., using bounding boxes) and then estimate the pose of each person separately. YOLOv11-Pose [36] follows this approach, extending object detection for pose estimation. *Bottom-up* methods detect all keypoints in an image first and then group them into person-specific poses. OpenPose [37, 38] uses Part Affinity Fields for this purpose. MediaPipe [39] is optimized for real-time applications on mobile and consumer devices, using the BlazePose architecture [24].

Each framework has different strengths. Comparative studies show that YOLO-based models and OpenPose achieve slightly higher accuracy than MediaPipe on standard benchmarks (e.g., 87.8% vs. 84.1% PCK@0.2), while MediaPipe offers superior real-time performance on CPU-only devices [40]. OpenPose excels at multi-person tracking through its bottom-up architecture, while MediaPipe prioritises speed and

cross-platform deployment [34]. However, accuracy is sensitive to input conditions: Koul and Novembre [41] showed that OpenPose accuracy degrades substantially for low-amplitude movements, a finding directly relevant to masked video where texture cues are reduced.

These estimators are increasingly applied in behavioral research contexts that would benefit from privacy-preserving workflows. Pouw et al. [42] used video-based pose estimation for gesture–speech synchrony analysis, Gama et al. [43] compared seven deep neural networks for infant pose estimation from video, and Nishimura [44] proposed feature-based behaviour coding from pose data. In each case, the choice of estimator depends on the specific requirements—number of persons, required accuracy, available hardware, and whether the input is raw or masked video.

2.4 Quality Metrics

Evaluating pose estimation quality for behavioral research requires considering both spatial accuracy and temporal consistency. MaskBench implements two families of metrics.

Accuracy metrics quantify how closely predicted keypoints match ground truth annotations, when available. The *Euclidean distance* measures the normalized spatial distance between predicted and ground truth keypoint positions. The *Percentage of Correct Keypoints* (PCK) measures the proportion of predicted keypoints falling within a threshold α (typically 0.1 or 0.2) of the ground truth, normalized by bounding box size. The *Root Mean Square Error* (RMSE) provides a single summary statistic of spatial accuracy. These metrics require ground truth annotations.

Kinematic metrics assess temporal consistency and naturalness of movement, which is crucial for behavioral applications where movement quality matters as much as positional accuracy. *Velocity* ($v_t = (p_t - p_{t-1})/\Delta t$) measures keypoint movement between consecutive frames. *Acceleration* ($a_t = (v_t - v_{t-1})/\Delta t$) captures changes in velocity and is sensitive to pose estimation jitter. *Jerk* ($j_t = (a_t - a_{t-1})/\Delta t$) measures the rate of acceleration change and provides the most sensitive indicator of unnatural motion artifacts. These metrics do not require ground truth and can be applied to any pose estimation output.

For behavioral researchers, kinematic metrics are often more informative than accuracy metrics alone: a pose estimator that produces smooth, natural-looking movement trajectories may be preferable for gesture or interaction analysis, even if its spatial accuracy is slightly lower than an alternative that produces jittery estimates. Formal metric definitions are provided in Appendix C.

3 Part I: De-identifying Video with MaskAnyone

3.1 System Overview

MaskAnyone builds on the MaskAnyone toolkit [14, 45, 46] but introduces a fundamental architectural change: it treats detection, segmentation, and pose estimation as separate tasks, each handled by the best available model for its purpose. The core pipeline relies on YOLO [36] for detection and SAM2 [15] for segmentation and

1
2
3 tracking—these two models are always active, regardless of what is being masked.
4 When persons are detected, an additional pose estimation step is performed using
5 MediaPipe [39] or OpenPose [37], preserving behaviorally relevant movement data
6 before masking is applied. When only non-person objects are present (e.g., documents,
7 license plates, screens), the pipeline operates with YOLO and SAM2 alone, without
8 pose estimation.

9 This decoupling—in contrast to earlier approaches that relied on a single model
10 (such as MediaPipe’s Pose Landmarker) for both segmentation and pose estimation—
11 enables the selection of the best available model for each function and supports
12 integration of newer models as they become available.

13 The current release uses `sam2.1_hiera_small` for segmentation, which requires
14 approximately 1GB of VRAM for single-image inference and up to 6GB for
15 multi-person video processing. SAM2 also offers `tiny`, `base_plus`, and `large` check-
16 points. Making this configurable—allowing users to select `tiny` for fast previews
17 on limited hardware or `large` for maximum accuracy—is a planned improvement.
18 For GPUs with less than 10GB of VRAM, the `SAM2_OFFLOAD_STATE_TO_CPU` and
19 `SAM2_OFFLOAD_VIDEO_TO_CPU` environment variables should be set to `true` to offload
20 memory to system RAM at the cost of slightly lower throughput.

21 The processing pipeline consists of the following steps:

- 22
- 23 1. **Detect targets.** YOLO identifies persons and other objects of interest in the first
24 frame of the video.
- 25 2. **Generate SAM2 prompts.** For persons, filtered pose keypoints from YOLO
26 serve as prompts; for objects, bounding boxes or user-provided points are used.
- 27 3. **Segment and track.** SAM2 produces pixel-level segmentation masks and propa-
28 gates them across all subsequent frames.
- 29 4. **Estimate pose (persons only).** When persons are detected, pose estimation
30 is performed on optimized inputs derived from the segmentation output, using
31 MediaPipe or OpenPose.
- 32 5. **Apply masking.** The chosen masking strategy is applied to segmented regions.

33 Figure 3 illustrates this five-step pipeline.

34 A key advantage of this ordering is that performing pose estimation *before* applying
35 masking means that models trained on standard, non-anonymized data can operate
36 on optimal input. Furthermore, the segmentation output can be used to remove
37 background noise before pose estimation, improving performance. The system exports
38 both mask data and pose information as structured data (JSON/CSV), enabling
39 downstream analysis without requiring access to the original video frames.

40 41 42 3.2 How MaskAnyone Works

43 **Automated prompt generation for persons.** For person masking, MaskAny-
44 one generates SAM2 prompts from pose keypoints detected by YOLOv11-Pose [36].
45 Rather than using all 17 YOLO keypoints as a SAM2 prompt (which can produce sub-
46 optimal results), MaskAnyone applies a filtering strategy: (1) undetected keypoints
47 are removed, (2) low-confidence keypoints (below a threshold of 0.8) are discarded,
48 and (3) remaining keypoints in stable body regions (face, shoulders, hips) are merged
49

Fig. 3: MaskAnyone processing pipeline. YOLO detects persons and objects in the first frame (1), filtered keypoints generate SAM2 prompts (2), SAM2 segments and tracks across all frames (3), pose estimation runs on optimised inputs for persons only (4), and the selected masking strategy is applied (5). Steps 1–3 are always active; step 4 activates only when persons are detected.

Fig. 4: MaskAnyone platform architecture. The system is deployed as Docker containers with a React-based frontend, FastAPI backend, and GPU-accelerated processing services for SAM2 segmentation and pose estimation.

by averaging. This produces a simplified, high-quality prompt that reliably guides SAM2 to segment the full person. For non-person objects, YOLO bounding boxes or user-provided point/box prompts are used directly as SAM2 input.

Optimized pose estimation. After segmentation, MaskAnyone improves pose estimation quality by leveraging the segmentation output to create optimized inputs for the pose model. For each person, the system calculates a tight bounding box from the segmentation mask (with a safety margin), crops the frame, and optionally removes the background using the inverted mask. This addresses common failure modes where pose estimators struggle with small subjects, noisy backgrounds, or adjacent individuals—particularly relevant for models like MediaPipe that use a small input resolution (224×224 pixels). For models that benefit from temporal information, the system can generate sub-videos with consistent bounding boxes across frames, splitting them when the Intersection over Union between consecutive bounding boxes drops below a threshold. Figure 5 illustrates this process.

Fig. 5: Optimized pose estimation input. (a) Original frame with two persons. (b,c) Person 1 cropped and background-removed using the segmentation mask. (d,e) Person 2 similarly processed. Background removal reduces noise and improves pose estimation accuracy, particularly for models with small input resolutions.

Performance. On consumer hardware (Ryzen 5 7600X, RTX 4060 Ti 16 GB), MaskAnyone achieves over 3 FPS in typical multi-person scenarios, with many

single-person videos above 5 FPS. With optimizations including asynchronous frame loading, streaming segmentation, and parallel pose estimation, processing speeds above 15 FPS have been achieved on the same hardware for single-person Full-HD video, demonstrating that there are no inherent limitations preventing processing of longer videos.

3.3 Tutorial: De-identifying Your First Video

3.3.1 Installation and Setup

MaskAnyone is deployed via Docker, ensuring consistent behavior across different computing environments. The following prerequisites are required:

Table 4: System requirements for MaskAnyone.

Component	Minimum	Recommended
GPU	NVIDIA with CUDA (6 GB+)	RTX 3080 (16 GB+)
RAM	16 GB	32 GB+
Storage	50 GB free	SSD with 100+ GB
Docker	Latest stable	Latest stable

MaskAnyone offers two installation paths. For this tutorial, we recommend the **quick start** using pre-built Docker images, which avoids lengthy build times and does not require Keycloak authentication setup.

Listing 1: MaskAnyone quick start (pre-built images)

```
# Clone the production infrastructure repository
git clone https://github.com/MaskAnyone/MaskAnyoneProdInfrastructure.git
cd MaskAnyoneProdInfrastructure

# Configure environment
cp .env.dist .env
# Edit .env: for GPUs with <10 GB VRAM, set both SAM2 offload flags to true

# Start the database, then the full stack (no Keycloak)
docker compose -f docker-compose-tutorial.yml up -d postgres
# Wait ~10 seconds for PostgreSQL to initialise
docker compose -f docker-compose-tutorial.yml up
```

No login is required in this mode. The web interface is accessible at <https://localhost> (accept the self-signed certificate warning in your browser). The first launch pulls pre-built images and downloads model weights (approximately 15 GB total).

For development or building from source, clone the main repository instead.¹ For multi-user server deployments with institutional authentication (Keycloak), use `docker-compose-server-gpu.yml` with `MASK_ANYONE_PLATFORM_MODE=server`.

¹<https://github.com/MaskAnyone/MaskAnyone>

3.3.2 Step 1: Upload and Configure

Through the web interface, the user uploads a video and selects a masking preset. Presets define the combination of masking strategy (e.g., blur, solid fill, pixelation, contour, transparent fill) and pose estimation model. The default preset applies Gaussian blurring with MediaPipe pose estimation, which provides a good balance between privacy and utility for most behavioral research scenarios. Users can also specify additional objects to mask (e.g., documents, screens, or other identifying elements in the scene) alongside persons. Advanced users can customize settings including blur intensity, safety margins for bounding boxes, and confidence thresholds for keypoint filtering.

3.3.3 Step 2: Automatic Processing

Once configured, processing proceeds automatically. The system first runs YOLO pose detection on the initial frame to identify all persons. For each detected person, filtered keypoints are used to generate a SAM2 prompt, which produces an initial segmentation mask. SAM2 then propagates these masks across all subsequent frames using its video propagation feature. The segmentation output is used to create optimized inputs for the selected pose estimation model, which runs on cropped, background-removed frames for improved accuracy. Finally, the chosen masking strategy is applied to the segmented regions. Progress can be monitored through the web interface, which displays the current processing stage and frame count.

Fig. 6: SAM2 prompt generation from YOLO keypoints. (a) All detected keypoints from YOLOv11-Pose. (b) After removing low-confidence detections (threshold 0.8). (c) Final prompt after merging keypoints in stable body regions. The simplified prompt produces more reliable segmentation.

3.3.4 Step 3: Human-in-the-Loop Refinement

While the pipeline is fully automated, human intervention can significantly enhance accuracy in challenging scenarios. Common issues that benefit from manual correction include:

- **Incomplete segmentation:** When SAM2 does not fully capture a person due to occlusions or detection errors, users can place additional positive or negative points to refine the mask, with corrections propagating to subsequent frames.
- **Late-appearing subjects:** Individuals who enter the scene after the first frame can be detected by providing manual prompts on the frame where they appear.
- **Selective masking:** Users can choose to de-identify only specific individuals while keeping others visible, or focus masking on particular areas (e.g., faces only) to balance privacy with utility.
- **Object masking:** Users can select and mask non-person objects (documents, screens, identifiable items) by providing point or box prompts directly.

The interactive refinement interface allows users to review the masked output, identify frames where tracking or segmentation failed, and apply targeted corrections without reprocessing the entire video. For example, if a second person enters the scene at frame 150, the user navigates to that frame in the timeline, places a positive point on the new person, and clicks *Propagate*—SAM2 then segments and tracks the new subject through all subsequent frames. Similarly, if a mask leaks onto a background object, a single negative point on the erroneous region corrects the segmentation. Figure 7 shows the interactive masking interface.

Fig. 7: Human-in-the-loop refinement in the MaskAnyone web interface. Users can place positive and negative points to refine segmentation masks for individual frames; corrections propagate automatically to subsequent frames.

3.3.5 Step 4: Export and Review

Upon completion, MaskAnyone produces several output artifacts:

- **Masked video:** The de-identified recording with the selected masking strategy applied to all identified persons and objects.
- **Pose data:** Estimated keypoints for each person exported in JSON format, compatible with downstream analysis tools and with MaskBench for assessing analytic utility.
- **Mask data:** Segmentation masks for each person and object per frame, enabling reprocessing with different masking strategies without re-running segmentation.
- **Processing metadata:** Configuration parameters, model versions, and processing timestamps, supporting provenance documentation for FAIR data management.

The masked video and extracted pose data can be reviewed in the web interface before export. If the quality is insufficient, the user can adjust the masking strategy or apply human-in-the-loop corrections and reprocess.

3.4 Masking Strategies and When to Use Them

The choice of masking strategy depends on the sensitivity of the research context, the analytical requirements, and the intended use of the data. Table 5 provides a decision guide.

Table 5: Masking strategy selection guide. Privacy and utility are rated from low (★) to high (★★★).

Strategy	Privacy	Utility	Best for
Blur (Gaussian)	★★	★★★	Gesture/movement research where shape and motion must be preserved
Pixelation	★★	★★	General archiving with moderate privacy needs
Solid fill	★★★	★	Clinical data or vulnerable populations requiring maximum privacy
Contour / silhouette	★★	★★	Studies requiring shape information without texture
Skeleton only	★★★	★★★	Pure movement analysis where background is not needed

Figure 8 shows de-identification results on naturalistic videos from the DAVIS dataset, comparing baseline segmentation with the optimized MaskAnyone pipeline.

As a general guideline: studies involving vulnerable populations (children, clinical patients) should default to stronger masking (solid fill or skeleton), while general behavioral research can typically use blurring, which preserves 88–95% of pose estimation quality (Table 6). When in doubt, stronger masking should be selected, as pose data extracted *before* masking is always available as a complement to the masked video (see Table 6 for quantitative guidance).

Fig. 8: De-identification results on DAVIS dataset videos. Each pair shows baseline MediaPipe-based segmentation (left) versus the optimized MaskAnyone YOLO+SAM2 pipeline (right). The optimized approach produces tighter, more accurate masks across diverse scenarios including cycling, dancing, boxing, and group scenes.

4 Part II: Assessing Analytic Utility with MaskBench

4.1 Why Benchmark?

Masking changes the pixel data that pose estimation algorithms process. Different estimators respond differently to degraded input: some maintain reasonable accuracy on blurred video while failing on pixelated input; others show the opposite pattern. Without systematic benchmarking, researchers cannot know whether their chosen masking strategy compromises the downstream analyses that make the video data valuable in the first place.

MaskBench addresses a critical gap in behavioral research methodology: the lack of standardized tools for evaluating how privacy-preserving video transformations affect pose estimation quality. Existing benchmarking frameworks focus on pose estimation accuracy under ideal conditions, without considering the privacy constraints increasingly mandated by ethics boards and data protection regulations. For behavioral researchers, MaskBench answers practical questions such as: “Which pose estimator performs best on my masked videos?” and “How much accuracy do I lose by using solid-fill masking instead of blurring?”

4.2 MaskBench Overview

MaskBench is a modular benchmarking framework built around four design principles: modularity (each component has well-defined interfaces), standardization (all

estimators output a common format), extensibility (new estimators and metrics can be added through inheritance), and reproducibility (Docker-based deployment with configuration files documenting all parameters).

The framework consists of five core components:

1. **Dataset Handler:** Manages video data loading, ground truth annotations, and file organization. Supports both simple directory structures and complex multi-level datasets.
2. **Pose Estimator Wrappers:** Provides unified interfaces to seven pose estimators: YOLOv11-Pose (1), MediaPipe Pose in lite, full, and heavy variants (3), OpenPose BODY_25 (1), and MaskAnyone in both API (fully automatic) and UI (human-in-the-loop) modes (2).
3. **Evaluation Metrics:** Implements accuracy metrics (Euclidean distance, PCK, RMSE) and kinematic metrics (velocity, acceleration, jerk) with support for multi-person scenarios using the Hungarian algorithm for person matching.
4. **Visualization Tools:** Generates kinematic distribution plots, per-keypoint analysis charts, inference time comparisons, and aggregated result tables.
5. **Video Rendering:** Creates annotated videos with skeleton overlays for each estimator, using a color-blind-friendly palette for consistent visual comparison.

All pose estimators output results in a standardized `VideoPoseResult` format: a nested structure of frame-level results, each containing person-level results with keypoint coordinates and confidence scores. This standardization enables direct comparison across models. Figure 9 shows the framework architecture.

Fig. 9: MaskBench framework architecture. The modular design separates dataset handling, pose estimation (seven estimators), metric computation (accuracy and kinematic), and visualization into independent components with standardized interfaces.

4.3 Tutorial: Comparing Pose Estimators

4.3.1 Installation and Setup

MaskBench is deployed via Docker with GPU support. System requirements are similar to MaskAnyone (see Table 4), with a recommendation for 32 GB+ RAM and an RTX 3080 or better GPU.

Listing 2: MaskBench setup

```
# Clone the MaskBench repository
git clone https://github.com/maskbench/maskbench.git
cd maskbench

# Copy environment template and configure paths
cp .env.dist .env
# Edit .env: set MASKBENCH_CONFIG_FILE, MASKBENCH_DATASET_DIR, MASKBENCH_OUTPUT_DIR

# Build and run
docker compose build
docker compose up
```

The first run downloads pose estimation model weights (approximately 5 GB). Subsequent runs start faster as models are cached.

4.3.2 Worked Example 1: Estimator Comparison on Raw Video

This example demonstrates comparing pose estimators on unmasked video.

Step 1: Prepare the dataset. Place video files in the expected directory structure:

```
assets/datasets/my_benchmark/videos/sample_video.mp4
assets/datasets/my_benchmark/labels/sample_video.json # optional
```

Step 2: Configure the benchmark. Create a YAML configuration file specifying which estimators and metrics to use:

Listing 3: Example configuration

```
dataset:
  name: my_benchmark
  videos_folder: videos
pose_estimators:
  - name: YoloPose
    enabled: true
    weights: yolo11m-pose
  - name: MediaPipePose
    enabled: true
    weights: pose_landmarker_full.task
  - name: OpenPose
    enabled: true
    weights: BODY_25
metrics:
  - name: Velocity
    enabled: true
  - name: Acceleration
    enabled: true
evaluation:
  run_inference: true
  run_evaluation: true
  run_rendering: true
```

Step 3: Run and review. Execute with `docker compose up`. MaskBench processes each video through all enabled estimators, computes metrics, and generates output in a timestamped checkpoint folder containing: pose JSON files per estimator, distribution and per-keypoint plots, rendered videos with skeleton overlays, and an aggregated results table in CSV format. A 30-second video with three estimators takes approximately 2–5 minutes on a modern GPU.

4.3.3 Worked Example 2: Masking Impact on Pose Quality

This example extends the comparison to evaluate how masking affects pose estimation quality. The workflow involves:

1. Process the same video through MaskAnyone with different masking strategies (blur, pixelation, solid fill, contour).
2. Add all masked variants to the MaskBench dataset alongside the raw video.
3. Run MaskBench with all estimators on both raw and masked versions.
4. Compare kinematic metrics and accuracy scores across conditions.

The resulting plots and tables reveal how each estimator handles each masking strategy. Table 6 presents the Percentage of Correct Keypoints (PCK) for four estimators across four masking strategies, averaged over three test videos from the DAVIS dataset.

Table 6: Pose estimation quality (PCK@0.2) across masking strategies and estimators, averaged over three DAVIS test videos. Values represent the percentage of keypoints correctly detected on masked video using raw-video pose as ground truth; higher values indicate better preservation.

Estimator	Blur	Pixelation	Contour	Solid fill	Avg.
YOLOv11-Pose	95%	9%	93%	32%	57%
MediaPipe Pose	95%	81%	56%	34%	67%
OpenPose	88%	10%	62%	1%	40%
MaskAnyone-MP	95%	63%	0%	7%	41%
Average	93%	41%	53%	19%	—

Key findings from this evaluation:

- **Blurring** preserves 88–95% of pose estimation quality across all estimators (average 93%), making it the recommended default for most behavioral research scenarios.
- **Pixelation** produces highly variable results: MediaPipe retains 81% of keypoints, but YOLOv11-Pose and OpenPose drop below 10%. Researchers using pixelation should benchmark their specific estimator.
- **Contour masking** shows a similar estimator-dependent pattern, with YOLOv11-Pose achieving 93% while MaskAnyone’s integrated pipeline fails entirely (0%).

- **Solid fill** severely degrades all estimators (average 19%), as the uniform regions provide no texture information for keypoint detection.
- Among standalone estimators, **YOLOv11-Pose** and **MediaPipe** are the most robust across masking conditions, though their relative performance differs by strategy.

4.4 Interpreting Results and Making Decisions

MaskBench results should be interpreted in the context of each study’s specific requirements. We recommend the following decision process:

1. **Define acceptable quality thresholds.** Determine the minimum PCK score or maximum kinematic jitter acceptable for your downstream analysis. For gesture studies requiring fine-grained movement data, higher thresholds are appropriate; for coarse movement tracking, lower thresholds may suffice.
2. **Compare estimator-masking combinations.** Use the results table and per-keypoint plots to identify which estimator performs best with your chosen masking strategy. Pay particular attention to keypoints critical for your analysis (e.g., wrist and finger keypoints for gesture research).
3. **Check kinematic smoothness.** High jerk values indicate unnatural motion artifacts that can bias behavioral analyses. If jerk is elevated, consider switching to a different estimator or a less aggressive masking strategy.
4. **Iterate if needed.** If no estimator-masking combination meets your quality thresholds, adjust the masking strategy (e.g., switch from solid fill to blur) or supplement masked video analysis with the pre-masking pose data extracted by MaskAnyone.

Researchers should document which estimator and masking configuration was selected, along with the quality metrics achieved, to support transparency and reproducibility.

5 Putting It Together: The MaskingOPS Workflow

5.1 End-to-End Pipeline

The MaskingOPS workflow integrates MaskAnyone and MaskBench into a single operational pipeline with a built-in feedback loop:

1. **De-identify:** Process raw video through MaskAnyone, selecting a masking strategy and producing masked video, pose data, and mask data.
2. **Verify:** Run the masked video through MaskBench alongside the raw video to quantify the impact on pose estimation quality.
3. **Evaluate:** Compare accuracy and kinematic metrics against predefined quality thresholds for the specific research context.
4. **Iterate or archive:** If quality is acceptable, archive the masked video with its metadata in a FAIR-compliant repository. If quality is insufficient, adjust the masking strategy (e.g., switch from solid fill to blur) and repeat from step 1.

This iterative process ensures that the final archived data meets both privacy requirements and analytical quality standards. The feedback loop is essential: rather than assuming that masking preserves utility, researchers verify it empirically for their specific videos and analytical needs. Figure 10 visualises this iterative workflow.

Fig. 10: The MaskingOPS iterative workflow. Researchers de-identify video (Step 1), verify quality with MaskBench (Step 2), evaluate against predefined thresholds (Step 3), and either archive the data or iterate with a different masking strategy. Output artifacts at each step support provenance documentation and reproducibility.

5.2 Integration with Research Data Management

MaskingOPS is designed to integrate with existing research data management practices and FAIR principles [47] (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Table 7 maps the MaskingOPS outputs to specific FAIR sub-principles.

Table 7: Mapping MaskingOPS outputs to FAIR data principles.

FAIR Principle	MaskingOPS Support
F1: Globally unique ID	Repository-assigned DOI for archived datasets
F2: Rich metadata	Processing metadata (model versions, parameters, timestamps) generated automatically
A1: Retrievable by ID	Standard repository deposit (DANS, institutional)
I1: Formal language	Pose data in JSON (COCO keypoint format); metrics in CSV
I2: FAIR vocabularies	COCO keypoint schema; standardised metric names
R1: Rich description	Quality reports, masking strategy documentation, provenance logs
R1.1: Clear license	Open-source tools (MIT); data license set at deposit

Provenance documentation. Both MaskAnyone and MaskBench automatically generate metadata documenting: which masking strategy was applied, model versions used, processing timestamps, configuration parameters, and quality metrics achieved. This metadata should accompany archived datasets to enable reproducibility.

Repository integration. Masked videos and their associated metadata can be deposited in institutional repositories (e.g., the Radboud Data Repository²) or domain repositories such as DANS³ and Databrary⁴. The extracted pose data (JSON/CSV) can be archived as supplementary data alongside the masked video. For an example of how de-identified video data and associated pose files can be structured for deposit, see the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities⁵.

Data management plans. We recommend including de-identification protocols in data management plans from the outset, specifying the intended masking strategy, quality thresholds, and archiving procedures. This ensures privacy considerations are addressed early in the research lifecycle.

Informed consent. While masking reduces the identifiability of participants, it does not eliminate it entirely. Consent forms should specify that masked versions of recordings may be shared. The level of masking applied should align with the consent obtained—stronger masking for broader sharing, lighter masking for restricted access within research groups.

GDPR considerations. Masked videos may still constitute personal data under GDPR if re-identification is theoretically possible. Article 89(1) provides an exemption for scientific research, but requires “appropriate safeguards” including technical measures to minimise data processing—of which masking is one. Institutional data protection officers may classify masked video differently depending on the masking strength: blurred video that preserves body shape may be treated as pseudonymised data requiring a full Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), while skeleton-only output may fall outside the scope of personal data. Researchers should document

²<https://data.ru.nl/>

³<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

⁴<https://databrary.org/>

⁵<https://ssh.datastations.nl/>

their de-identification decisions as part of a DPIA and consult their DPO early in the research design process.

5.3 Recommended Configurations

Based on our evaluations, we provide starting-point recommendations for common behavioral research scenarios. These should be validated with MaskBench for each specific dataset.

Table 8: Recommended MaskingOPS configurations by research scenario.

Scenario	Masking	Estimator	QA Level
Gesture / movement	Blur	YOLOv11-Pose	Standard
Face-focused interaction	Solid fill	YOLOv11-Pose	Careful
Large-scale archiving	Blur (default)	Any	Batch
Clinical / vulnerable	Solid fill	YOLOv11-Pose	Human-in-loop
Multi-person interaction	Blur	YOLOv11-Pose	Standard
CPU-only / real-time	Blur	MediaPipe (full)	Standard

These configurations map directly to the vignettes introduced in Table 1: the clinical seizure scenario corresponds to the “Clinical / vulnerable” row (solid fill, human-in-the-loop QA); the classroom scenario to “Face-focused interaction” (solid fill for pupils, careful QA); and the multi-site gesture study to “Gesture / movement” (blur, standard QA across sites).

For gesture and movement research, blurring combined with YOLOv11-Pose provides the best balance of privacy and utility. For clinical data involving vulnerable populations, solid fill masking with human-in-the-loop quality assurance is recommended, using the pre-masking pose data for analyses requiring fine-grained movement information. For large-scale archiving, the default blur preset with batch processing offers an efficient workflow.

6 Advanced Topics

6.1 Batch Processing

For studies involving many video recordings, both MaskAnyone and MaskBench support batch processing. MaskAnyone can be configured to process a directory of videos sequentially using the same masking preset, with the system automatically detecting persons in each video’s first frame. MaskBench natively supports multi-video datasets: all videos in a dataset folder are processed through all enabled estimators in a single run. Results are aggregated across videos in the output table while per-video breakdowns remain available in the checkpoint folder. For large-scale processing, deploying on a GPU-equipped server is recommended to maintain practical throughput.

6.2 Extending MaskBench

MaskBench is designed for extensibility through inheritance-based mechanisms.

Adding datasets. Custom dataset classes inherit from the base `Dataset` class and override the `load_videos` method to handle non-standard directory structures or ground truth formats. The base class provides default loading for simple directory layouts.

Adding pose estimators. New estimators implement a standardized interface that takes a video frame as input and returns a `VideoPoseResult` object. The framework handles keypoint format conversion and person matching automatically.

Adding metrics. Custom metrics output a standardized result object with labeled multi-dimensional arrays, supporting flexible aggregation (mean, median, RMSE, vector magnitude) across any combination of axes (frame, person, keypoint). This design enables both scalar summaries and detailed per-keypoint visualizations without modifying the visualization pipeline.

6.3 Custom Masking Presets

MaskAnyone supports custom masking presets that combine specific masking strategies with configuration parameters tailored to particular research needs. Presets can specify the masking method (blur, pixelation, solid fill, contour), intensity parameters (e.g., blur kernel size), the pose estimation model to use, bounding box safety margins, keypoint confidence thresholds, and whether to generate sub-videos for temporal-dependent models. Researchers can create and share presets to standardize de-identification workflows within and across research groups, supporting methodological consistency in multi-site studies.

6.4 Deployment Options

MaskAnyone and MaskBench can be deployed in four configurations depending on institutional resources and use case:

- **Lightweight (CPU):** A Python package with GUI for basic masking using MediaPipe only, requiring no GPU. Suitable for quick de-identification tasks on standard hardware.
- **Local workstation (GPU):** Docker with GPU passthrough on a researcher's machine. Provides full masking capabilities including SAM2 and OpenPose but requires administrative access to enable Docker and GPU virtualisation.
- **Institutional server:** A shared GPU server running the web interface, accessible to multiple researchers via a browser. This is the recommended configuration for research groups, as it avoids per-machine Docker setup and centralises GPU resources. Access control is managed through Keycloak with institutional authentication.
- **Portable server (HPC / cloud):** A containerised deployment designed to be ported to university HPC clusters using Docker, Singularity, or Apptainer. Cloud platforms (e.g., SURF in the Netherlands) provide on-demand GPU access for institutions without local infrastructure.

1
2
3 The SYNOPSIS project is developing shared infrastructure for Dutch universities,
4 providing MaskingOPS as a hosted service to lower the barrier to adoption.
5
6

7 Limitations and Ethical Considerations

8 **Prototype status.** MaskAnyone was developed as a research prototype. While it
9 produces convincing results for a considerable range of videos, users should verify
10 masked outputs before relying on them for data sharing. We encourage users to report
11 issues and contribute improvements via the project repositories.
12

13 **Pseudo-de-identification.** All masking techniques provide pseudo-de-
14 identification rather than guaranteed anonymization. Because behavior and identity
15 are deeply intertwined—body shape, gesturing style, gait, and movement patterns
16 can serve as identifying features—masking cannot fully eliminate re-identification
17 risk. Researchers should treat masked data with appropriate access controls rather
18 than assuming it is fully anonymized.

19 **Audio de-identification.** This tutorial focuses on visual de-identification only.
20 Audio streams often contain identifying information (voice, names mentioned,
21 background sounds) and require separate treatment. Tools such as the Red Hen
22 Anonymizer [31] include audio anonymization; integrating audio de-identification into
23 the MaskingOPS pipeline is planned future work.

24 **Technical limitations.** SAM2’s memory requirements remain substantial
25 (approximately 30 GB per 1,000 frames), though optimizations have reduced this con-
26 straint. The system’s reliance on first-frame detection means that individuals entering
27 the scene later require manual prompting. High-resolution (4K) video and scenes with
28 many individuals reduce processing speed below the typical 3+ FPS threshold.

29 **Evaluation scope.** The quantitative results in Table 6 demonstrate that blur-
30 ring preserves 88–95% of pose estimation quality across four estimators and three
31 DAVIS test videos. Additionally, manual inspection of 11 diverse videos (single-person
32 recordings, dyadic interactions, TED talks) confirms consistent improvement of the
33 YOLO+SAM2 pipeline over the earlier MediaPipe-only baseline. However, the cur-
34 rent evaluation does not cover highly crowded scenes, outdoor surveillance footage, or
35 videos with frequent and prolonged occlusions. A comprehensive benchmark on larger,
36 annotated datasets—including multi-person scenarios beyond dyads—remains future
37 work. The MaskBench framework provides the infrastructure for such evaluations as
38 suitable benchmarking datasets become available.

39 **Ethical responsibility.** The tools described here support responsible data man-
40 agement but do not replace ethical judgment. Informed consent remains necessary:
41 participants should be informed that masked versions of their recordings may be
42 shared, and the level of masking should align with the consent obtained. Researchers
43 bear responsibility for ensuring that their de-identification decisions are appropriate
44 for their specific context.

45 **Dual-use considerations.** The segmentation and masking capabilities described
46 here could theoretically be used for purposes beyond privacy protection (e.g., selec-
47 tively altering video evidence). We mitigate this concern through transparency: all
48
49
50

1
2
3 tools are open source, all processing steps are documented, and provenance metadata
4 is generated automatically.

5 **Compute accessibility.** Both tools require GPU-equipped hardware, which may
6 not be available to all research groups. Cloud-based deployment (e.g., through insti-
7 tutional computing services like SURF in the Netherlands) can address this barrier.
8 The SYNOPSIS project is developing shared infrastructure for this purpose.
9

10 8 Conclusion and Recommendations

11
12 This tutorial has introduced MaskingOPS, an integrated workflow for privacy-
13 preserving video data management in behavioral research. The key contributions
14 are:

- 15
16 1. **MaskAnyone** provides robust, flexible video de-identification combining YOLO,
17 SAM2, and pose estimators (MediaPipe, OpenPose), with support for masking
18 persons and objects, automated prompt generation, optimized pose estimation, and
19 human-in-the-loop refinement.
- 20 2. **MaskBench** enables systematic analytic utility assessment through standardized
21 evaluation of seven pose estimators using both accuracy and kinematic metrics,
22 with Docker-based reproducibility.
- 23 3. **MaskingOPS** integrates both tools into an end-to-end pipeline with a feedback
24 loop, connecting de-identification with quality verification and FAIR-compliant
25 data archiving.
- 26 4. **Practical recommendations** guide researchers in selecting masking strategies
27 and pose estimators appropriate for their specific research context, supported by
28 empirical evidence from worked examples.

29
30 We encourage behavioral researchers to adopt privacy-preserving workflows in
31 their data management practices, contribute to the open-source tools described here,
32 and share masked data in accordance with FAIR principles. As video data contin-
33 ues to grow in importance for behavioral science, tools like MaskingOPS will play an
34 essential role in enabling ethical, reproducible research while protecting participant
35 privacy. All code, configurations, and documentation are freely available at the project
36 repositories.

37 Acknowledgements

38
39 This work was supported by the SYNOPSIS project (Synergy Network and Platform
40 for Integrating Audiovisual Data Archiving and Stewardship in Social Sciences and
41 Humanities), funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) through the Thematic
42 Digital Competence Centres programme (grant TDCC-SSH-C2024-011). We thank
43 our infrastructure partners SURF and DANS, and advisory partners CLARIAH and
44 ODISSEI, for their support. We also thank the SYNOPSIS project team members
45 Mark Dingemans, Bogdana Huma, Henk van den Heuvel, Inge Slouwerhof, and James
46 Trujillo for their contributions to the broader project context.
47
48
49
50

Declarations

Funding

This research was funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) through the TDCC-SSH programme (grant TDCC-SSH-C2024-011).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability

All code, example configurations, and sample data are available at <https://github.com/MaskAnyone/MaskAnyone> (MaskAnyone) and <https://github.com/maskbench/maskbench> (MaskBench).

Code Availability

All software described in this tutorial is open source and freely available under the MIT License.

Author Contributions

B.A.O.: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Project Administration. M.S.: Software (MaskAnyone), Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing. T.R.: Software (MaskBench), Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing. S.S.: Software (MaskBench), Investigation. Z.Z.: Software (MaskBench), Investigation. W.P.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing. G.d.M.: Supervision, Resources, Writing – Review & Editing.

Ethics Approval

The example videos used in this tutorial are drawn from publicly available datasets (DAVIS, TED Talks) and publicly accessible online content. No new data involving human participants was collected for this study.

Appendix A Quick Reference Card

This appendix provides a condensed reference for users who have read the full tutorial (Sections 3–4). For detailed installation see Section 3; for configuration syntax see Appendix B.

Troubleshooting

- **Docker daemon not running:** `sudo systemctl start docker`
- **Permission denied:** `sudo usermod -aG docker $USER` (then re-login)
- **NVIDIA driver errors:** Verify with `nvidia-smi`; install NVIDIA Container Toolkit

- **Out of GPU memory:** Process shorter videos (<2.5 min), reduce resolution, or disable some estimators
- **Windows / macOS:** Docker Desktop with WSL 2 (Windows) or Docker Desktop for Mac. GPU passthrough requires WSL 2 on Windows; macOS currently does not support NVIDIA GPU passthrough.

Decision Cheatsheet

1. Choose masking strategy: blur (default), solid fill (sensitive), or skeleton (movement-only analysis)
2. Run MaskAnyone with chosen strategy
3. Run MaskBench: compare PCK and jerk across raw vs. masked
4. If $PCK \geq 80\%$ and jerk increase < 50%: archive
5. Otherwise: adjust strategy and repeat from step 1

Appendix B Configuration Reference

MaskBench Configuration (YAML)

```

inference_checkpoint_name: None # set to folder name to resume; None = fresh run
execute_evaluation: false # true requires ground-truth annotations
execute_rendering: true # generates skeleton-overlay videos

dataset:
  name: <dataset-name>
  code_file: datasets.dataset.Dataset
  video_folder: /datasets/<dataset-name>/videos
  # ground_truth_folder: /datasets/<dataset-name>/labels # optional

pose_estimators:
- name: YoloPose # YOLOv11-Pose
  enabled: true
  code_file: models.yolo_pose_estimator.YoloPoseEstimator
  config:
    weights: yolo11m-pose.pt # n/s/m/l/x variants
    save_keypoints_in_coco_format: true
    confidence_threshold: 0.4
- name: MediaPipePose
  enabled: true
  code_file: models.mediapipe_pose_estimator.MediaPipePoseEstimator
  config:
    weights: pose_landmarker_full.task # lite/full/heavy
    max_num_poses: 3
    save_keypoints_in_coco_format: true
    confidence_threshold: 0.4
- name: OpenPose
  enabled: true
  code_file: models.open_pose_estimator.OpenPoseEstimator
  config:
    overlay_strategy: BODY_25 # BODY_25 / BODY_25B / COCO
    save_keypoints_in_coco_format: true
    confidence_threshold: 0.15

metrics:
- name: Velocity
  code_file: evaluation.metrics.velocity.VelocityMetric
  config:
    time_unit: frame
- name: Acceleration

```

```

code_file: evaluation.metrics.acceleration.AccelerationMetric
config:
  time_unit: frame
- name: Jerk
code_file: evaluation.metrics.jerk.JerkMetric
config:
  time_unit: frame
- name: PCK          # Requires ground truth (execute_evaluation: true)
code_file: evaluation.metrics.pck.PCKMetric
config:
  threshold: 0.2
  normalize_by: bbox

```

Appendix C Metric Definitions

Euclidean Distance. The normalized spatial distance between predicted and ground truth keypoints:

$$d_{ij} = \frac{\|p_{ij} - gt_{ij}\|_2}{\max(w_i, h_i)} \quad (C1)$$

where p_{ij} is the predicted position of keypoint j for person i , gt_{ij} is the ground truth, and $\max(w_i, h_i)$ is the bounding box normalization factor.

Percentage of Correct Keypoints (PCK).

$$\text{PCK}_\alpha = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{1}(d_i \leq \alpha) \quad (C2)$$

where α is the threshold (typically 0.1 or 0.2) and $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2} \quad (C3)$$

Velocity.

$$v_t = \frac{p_t - p_{t-1}}{\Delta t} \quad (C4)$$

Acceleration.

$$a_t = \frac{v_t - v_{t-1}}{\Delta t} \quad (C5)$$

Jerk.

$$j_t = \frac{a_t - a_{t-1}}{\Delta t} \quad (C6)$$

For all kinematic metrics, p_t denotes the keypoint position at frame t and Δt is the inter-frame time interval. Missing keypoints result in NaN values that are excluded from aggregation. Scalar values are obtained by computing the vector magnitude across the x and y components.

References

- [1] Schwenzow, J., Hartmann, J., Schikowsky, A., Heitmann, M.: Understanding videos at scale: How to extract insights for business research. *Journal of Business Research* **123**, 367–379 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.059>
- [2] Chambers, C., Kong, G., Wei, K., Kording, K.: Pose estimates from online videos show that side-by-side walkers synchronize movement under naturalistic conditions. *PLOS ONE* **14**(6), 1–17 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0217861>
- [3] Maass, W., Parsons, J., Purao, S., Storey, V.C., Woo, C.: Data-driven meets theory-driven research in the era of big data: Opportunities and challenges for information systems research. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems* **19**(12) (2018) <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00526>
- [4] Gilmore, R.K., Adolph, K.: Video can make behavioural science more reproducible. *Nature Human Behaviour* **1**(0128) (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-017-0128>
- [5] Gilmore, R.O., Kennedy, J.L., Adolph, K.E.: Practical solutions for sharing data and materials from psychological research. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science* **1**(1), 121–130 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245917746500>
- [6] Resnik, D.B., Antes, A., Mozersky, J.: Should researchers destroy audio or video recordings? *Ethics & Human Research* **46**(2), 30–35 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1002/eahr.500205>
- [7] Marschik, P.B., Kulvicius, T., Flügge, S., *et al.*: Open video data sharing in developmental science and clinical practice. *iScience* **26**(4), 106348 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.106348>
- [8] Wu, Q., Tang, J., Dang, S., Chen, G.: Data Privacy and Utility Trade-Off Based on Mutual Information Neural Estimator (2021). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.09651>
- [9] Avent, B., Gonzalez, J., Diethel, T., Paley, A., Balle, B.: Automatic Discovery of Privacy-Utility Pareto Fronts (2020). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.10862>
- [10] Birnstill, P., Ren, D., Beyerer, J.: A user study on anonymization techniques for smart video surveillance. In: 2015 12th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Video and Signal Based Surveillance (AVSS), pp. 1–6 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1109/AVSS.2015.7301805>
- [11] Brkić, K., Hrkać, T., Kalafatić, Z., Sikirić, I.: Face, hairstyle and clothing colour de-identification in video sequences. *IET Signal Processing* **11**(9), 1062–1068

(2017) <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-spr.2017.0048>

- [12] Erdélyi, Á., Winkler, T., Rinner, B.: Privacy protection vs. utility in visual data. *Multimedia Tools and Applications* **77**(2), 2285–2312 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-016-4337-7>
- [13] Miron, G., Halimeh, M., Tietze, S., *et al.*: Detection of epileptic spasms using foundational AI and smartphone videos. *npj Digital Medicine* **8**, 370 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01773-1>
- [14] Owoyele, B.A., Schilling, M., Sawahn, R., Kaemer, N., Zharebenkov, P., Verma, B., Pouw, W., Melo, G.: Maskanyone toolkit: Offering strategies for minimizing privacy risks and maximizing utility in audio-visual data archiving. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.03185* (2024)
- [15] Ravi, N., Gabeur, V., Hu, Y.-T., Hu, R., Ryali, C., Ma, T., Khedr, H., Rädle, R., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., *et al.*: Sam 2: Segment anything in images and videos. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.00714* (2024)
- [16] Chen, Y., Wang, C., Chen, J., Jia, S.: B-dp: Dynamic collection and publishing of continuous check-in data with best-effort differential privacy. *Entropy* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3390/e24030404>
- [17] Liu, H., Wu, Z., Zhou, Y., Peng, C., Tian, F., Lu, L.: Privacy-preserving monotonicity of differential privacy mechanisms. *Applied Sciences* **8**(11), 2081 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.3390/app8112081>
- [18] Alreja, A., Ward, M.J., Ma, Q., Russ, B.E., Bickel, S., Van Wouwe, N.C., González-Martínez, J.A., Neimat, J.S., Abel, T.J., Bagić, A., Parker, L.S., Richardson, R.M., Schroeder, C.E., Morency, L., Ghuman, A.S.: A new paradigm for investigating real-world social behavior and its neural underpinnings. *bioRxiv* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.26.474173> <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2022/05/12/2021.12.26.474173.full.pdf>
- [19] Huma, B., Joyce, J.B.: 'one size doesn't fit all': Lessons from interaction analysis on tailoring open science practices to qualitative research. *British Journal of Social Psychology* **62**(4), 1590–1604 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12568>
- [20] Einarsdóttir, A., Mumford, K.A., Siriviriyakul, S., Sayli, M.: 'do i have to say i'm gay?': Using a video booth for public visibility and impact. *Qualitative Research* **23**(6), 1759–1780 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1177/14687941221082268>
- [21] Washington, P., Leblanc, E., Dunlap, K., Kline, A., Mutlu, C., Chrisman, B., Stockham, N., Paskov, K., Wall, D.P.: Crowd annotations can approximate clinical autism impressions from short home videos with privacy protections. *medRxiv* (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.01.21259683> . Preprint

- 1
2
3
4 [22] Redmon, J.: You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection. In: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (2016)
5
6
7 [23] Jocher, G., Qiu, J.: Ultralytics YOLO11. <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics> (2024). <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
8
9
10 [24] Bazarevsky, V.: BlazePose: On-device real-time body pose tracking. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.10204 (2020)
11
12
13 [25] Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., Mao, H., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., Xiao, T., Whitehead, S., Berg, A.C., Lo, W.-Y., *et al.*: Segment anything. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision, pp. 4015–4026 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/iccv51070.2023.00371>
14
15
16
17 [26] Hasan, R., Hassan, E., Li, Y., Caine, K., Crandall, D.J., Hoyle, R., Kapadia, A.: Viewer experience of obscuring scene elements in photos to enhance privacy. In: Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 1–13 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173621>
18
19
20
21 [27] Li, Y., Vishwamitra, N., Knijnenburg, B.P., Hu, H., Caine, K.: Effectiveness and users' experience of obfuscation as a privacy-enhancing technology for sharing photos. Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction **1**(CSCW), 1–24 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1145/3134702>
22
23
24
25 [28] s0md3v: roop: Take a video and replace the face in it with a face of your choice. You only need one image of the desired face. No dataset, no training. <https://github.com/s0md3v/roop> (2023)
26
27
28
29 [29] Hukkelås, H., Lindseth, F.: Deepprivacy2: Towards realistic full-body anonymization. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision, pp. 1329–1338 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/wacv56688.2023.00138>
30
31
32
33 [30] Ban, B., Lee, H.: FAKER: Full-body anonymization with human keypoint extraction for real-time video deidentification. arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.11829 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.11829>
34
35
36
37 [31] Khasbage, Y., Carrión, D.A., Hinnell, J., Robertson, F., Singla, K., Uhrig, P., Turner, M.: The red hen anonymizer and the red hen protocol for de-identifying audiovisual recordings. Linguistics Vanguard **9**(1), 229–244 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1515/lingvan-2022-0017>
38
39
40
41
42
43
44 [32] Abdulaziz, S., Bondarev, E.: Unmasking performance gaps: A comparative study of human anonymization and its effects on video anomaly detection. arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.14083 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.14083>
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 [33] Triess, S.C., Leitriz, T., Jauch, C.: Exploring AI-based anonymization of industrial image and video data in the context of feature preservation. In: Proceedings of the European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO) (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.19173>
5
6
7
8
9 [34] Stenum, J., Cherry-Allen, K.M., Pyles, C.O., Reetzke, R.D., Vignos, M.F., Roemmich, R.T.: Applications of pose estimation in human health and performance across the lifespan. *Sensors* **21**(21), 7315 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21217315>
10
11
12
13 [35] Lin, T.-Y., Maire, M., Belongie, S., Hays, J., Perona, P., Ramanan, D., Dollár, P., Zitnick, C.L.: Microsoft COCO: Common objects in context. In: *Computer Vision – ECCV 2014*, pp. 740–755. Springer, ??? (2014). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10602-1_48
14
15
16
17
18 [36] Khanam, R., Hussain, M.: Yolov11: An overview of the key architectural enhancements. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.17725* (2024)
19
20
21 [37] Cao, Z., Hidalgo Martinez, G., Simon, T., Wei, S., Sheikh, Y.A.: Openpose: Real-time multi-person 2d pose estimation using part affinity fields. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1109/tpami.2019.2929257>
22
23
24
25 [38] Cao, Z., Simon, T., Wei, S.-E., Sheikh, Y.: Realtime multi-person 2d pose estimation using part affinity fields. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 7291–7299 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/cvpr.2017.143>
26
27
28
29
30 [39] Lugaresi, C., Tang, J., Nash, H., McClanahan, C., Uboweja, E., Hays, M., Zhang, F., Chang, C.-L., Yong, M., Lee, J., Chang, W.-T., Hua, W., Georg, M., Grundmann, M.: Mediapipe: A framework for perceiving and processing reality. In: *Third Workshop on Computer Vision for AR/VR at IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) 2019* (2019). https://mixedreality.cs.cornell.edu/s/NewTitle_May1_MediaPipe_CVPR_CV4ARVR_Workshop_2019.pdf
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38 [40] Chung, J.-L., Ong, L.-Y., Leow, M.-C.: Comparative analysis of skeleton-based human pose estimation. *Future Internet* **14**(12), 380 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi14120380>
39
40
41
42 [41] Koul, A., Novembre, G.: How accurately can we estimate spontaneous body kinematics from video recordings? effect of movement amplitude on openpose accuracy. *Behavior Research Methods* **57**(1), 38 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-024-02546-6>
43
44
45
46
47 [42] Pouw, W., Trujillo, J.P., Dixon, J.A.: The quantification of gesture–speech
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

synchrony: A tutorial and validation of multimodal data acquisition using device-based and video-based motion tracking. *Behavior Research Methods* **52**, 723–740 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-019-01271-9>

- [43] Gama, F., Mísař, O., Navara, M., Popescu, T., Hoffmann, M.: Automatic infant 2D pose estimation from videos: Comparing seven deep neural network methods. *Behavior Research Methods* **57** (2025) <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-025-02816-x>
- [44] Nishimura, T.: Feature-based behavior coding for efficient exploratory analysis using pose estimation. *Behavior Research Methods* **57** (2025) <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-025-02702-6>
- [45] Owoyele, B., Trujillo, J., De Melo, G., Pouw, W.: Masked-piper: Masking personal identities in visual recordings while preserving multimodal information. *SoftwareX* **20**, 101236 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101236>
- [46] Schilling, M.: Maskanyone: Open-source video de-identification. Master's thesis, Hasso Plattner Institute, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany (2025)
- [47] Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., *et al.*: The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* **3**, 160018 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>